

Local Government in Italy

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Italy: An Introduction

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According to Article 5 of the Italian Constitution, '[the Republic] implements the fullest measure of administrative decentralization in those services which depend on the State'. Article 118, indeed, attributes all administrative functions to the most decentralized level of government, i.e. the municipalities, 'unless they are attributed to the provinces, metropolitan cities and regions or to the State, pursuant to the principles of subsidiarity, differentiation and proportionality'. Furthermore, according to Article 117, the fundamental functions of Italian local government (i.e. municipalities, provinces and metropolitan cities) are to be determined by the State, that has exclusive legislative powers in this matter.

The Fiscal Federalism Law no 42/2009 gives the most comprehensive overview over these fundamental functions assigned by the State. Accordingly, it considers municipalities to be in charge of their own general administration, management and control; local police; public education (including early childhood education and care from 0-3 years, educational support, meals, and construction); transport and roads; territorial and environmental management; and social services (Article 21(3)). According to Law no 56/2014 'Delrio', the provinces are in charge of, among others, territorial planning and environmental protection; provincial public transport and provincial streets; the provincial school network and the management of school buildings; providing technical-administrative assistance to local entities; the promotion of equal opportunity, their own strategic development and institutional relations with other territorial entities (Articles 85-86).

On top of these provincial functions, the state has assigned additional tasks to the relatively young metropolitan cities, most of which are linked to specific urban challenges, such as adopting a strategic plan for the metropolitan territory; general spatial planning including infrastructure and communication networks; the structuring and coordination of metropolitan public services; mobility and roads, especially ensuring the compatibility and coherence of municipal urban planning on the metropolitan territory; economic and social development; as well as the promotion and coordination of digitalization and information technologies (Law no 56/2014 'Delrio').

As the regions have (concurrent) legislative powers in many matters (e.g. social welfare, education, culture, town planning, housing, regional transport, maintenance of roads and the public transport net, economic development, commerce, waste management, policing; Article 117 of the Italian Constitution), they may also attribute functions to the local entities on their territory. Because of certain historical legacies, size or political cultures, some regions might favor greater administrative decentralization than others and recent structural reforms have

led to the up-scaling of formerly provincial functions to the regional level.⁵ Overall, this leads to a highly differentiated, complex and evolving picture of local – i.e. municipal, provincial and metropolitan – functions in Italy.

Overall, the fragmented legislation regarding municipal functions has led to strong bottom-up dynamics in the interpretation of municipal responsibilities and instruments for service delivery. Indeed, Italian municipalities can revert to a wide variety of instruments for the delivery of their services, which range from public institutions entirely dependent on the municipality to public companies that are simultaneously employed by multiple municipalities to private non-profit organizations or public-private partnerships.⁶

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Bolgherini S, Lippi A and Maset S, 'In mezzo al guado: La governance subregionale tra "vecchie" province e "nuove" aree vaste' (2016) 3 *Rivista Italiana di Politiche Pubbliche* 341

Lippi A and Profeti S, 'Where is Politics in Corporatisation? Local Public Services from Policy to Politics in Continental Europe' (2014) 1 *Rivista Italiana di Politiche Pubbliche* 5

⁵ For an overview over how the 15 regions with ordinary statute have re-allocated provincial functions, see Tab. 2 of Silvia Bolgherini, Andrea Lippi and Sergio Maset, 'In mezzo al guado: La governance subregionale tra "vecchie" province e "nuove" aree vaste' (2016) 3 *Rivista Italiana di Politiche Pubbliche* 341, 39. 4

⁶ Andrea Lippi and Stefania Profeti, 'Where is Politics in Corporatisation? Local Public Services from Policy to Politics in Continental Europe' (2014) 1 *Rivista Italiana di Politiche Pubbliche* 5, 14f.

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